

A CASE STUDY OF FLEXIBLE PACKAGING USING LEAN METHODOLOGY

Andreja Pogačar ¹, Jure Miklavc ², Miha Klinar ²

¹ Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, Ljubljana, Slovenia

² Academy of fine arts and design, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Professional paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3416731
hello@dodopack.com

Abstract: *The situation that I'm dealing with here is a transport packaging for different sizes and shapes of bottles. Most used packaging by my client is sufficient for approximately 30% types of the bottles that they distribute. The empty space is filled with plastic flakes. After several phases of testing we made a flexible corrugated cardboard packaging in two sizes. It is suitable for more than 95% of the different shaped bottles that the client distributes. The packages are custom made, the pricing is competitive, it allows personalized print, is easy to assemble, requires no plastic flakes and meets the requirements of the circular economy. is an environmentally friendly solution and it is easy to recycle.*

Key words: case study, flexible, packaging, corrugated, cardboard, structural, design, lean methodology

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging on its own is a waste, but the quality of its design depends on the efficiency of delivery, the protection of the product during transportation and also has the effect of after-sales.

During the research phase, I found a client who needed a packaging solution, and together we developed an item of flexible packaging using lean methodology. The company Flaviar Ltd. is engaged in the distribution of higher price alcoholic beverages. They offer tasting packages containing five small bottles and standard bottled alcoholic beverages. The client offers his services primarily through their website, mobile application and social media. With the

expansion of the market, sales are growing and this leads to the need to solve the bottle packaging problem. The client is aware that packaging is an important touchpoint that can stimulate both positive and negative emotions in their customers, thus enabling or failing to resell and build a robust, trusted brand. Their key markets are the United States and in Europe, Great Britain and Germany. Complaints received from their customers average 1% on a monthly basis and can be up to 3%. They are always due to damaged or broken content.

Until my involvement in the project, the client was ordering transport packaging for bottles from the Post Office of Slovenia. Their standard packaging is narrow and oblong, the empty space is filled with plastic flakes. Larger bottles that don't fit are packaged in oversized packaging using additional plastic flakes.

Consumers are increasingly becoming aware of packaging waste and the damaging effects it has on the environment. Sustainable packaging that is reusable, recyclable, compostable or biodegradable is the way to go (Singh & Sarkar, 2019).

Reducing the weight of the packaging and by stripping away any non-essential elements, offering a simple graphic design, with less printed area and the use of ecological ink, affects both the environment and means a lower cost across the entire supply chain. It is important that it provides sufficient protection for the product, gives a positive experience to the end user and that its impact on the environment after the end of life is minimal or in perfect circumstances zero (Batista, 2018).

Cardboard is definitely one of the simplest materials for recycling, in 2013 about 79% of paper was recycled in Slovenia (Bernard Vukadin, Lipovž-Ančik and Zupančič, 2019). Paper fibres can be recycled six to seven times. The common choice of corrugated cardboard packaging is due to the fact that it is environmentally friendly and easy to recycle. The recycling of recyclates in basic materials does not crucially affect the packaging function itself. Recycling of cardboard packaging is extremely successful. Nowadays, cardboard packaging is recycled like any other material.

Material benefits are durability, versatility, lightweight with a good balance between strength and weight (low weight affects the entire transport route), it is made from a renewable source, flexible, offers sufficient protection, stands out with its visual appearance, cost-effective (low cost of production, storage, flattened packaging takes up less space), compared to other market alternatives, this material is among the most affordable. Weakness is when it comes into contact with moisture or liquid, it gets deformed or even torn

(there are already various coatings that protect the material from moisture, but these also influence the final packaging price and the recyclability of the material). The material is not suitable for extreme pressures when the packaging is stacked together, the problem is also in the processing of the material itself, the chemicals used in the manufacturing process, adhesives used for the structural part of the packaging, the chemical composition of printing inks. Lamination added to the cardboard make is non recyclable and pollutes the raw material in the process of recycling.

In Europe recycling has increased by 49% (19.5 million tonnes) since 1998, the base year for the first voluntary commitment set in the European Declaration on Paper Recycling. The recycling rate in Europe increased to 72.3% in 2017. The recycling paper rate in 2016 for North America was 67.4%, for Asia 52.6%, Latin America 46.4% and for Africa 37.2% (European paper recycling council , 2017). Recycling helps to reduce the amount of waste in landfills. Also, discarded cardboard represents a raw material from which we make new products and materials.

The packaging made of corrugated board must take into consideration eco-design guidelines (European Commission, 2017) and the requirements of the circular economy. The best way is when we develop packaging while having the end life of use in mind.

Everyone has had experience with packaging that could not be opened. Client loyalty is also built up by preventing situations like this. So, a frustration free packaging opening experience is a very important point (Lorenzini and Olsson, 2019).

Offering personalised packaging is a great way to build a lasting connection with your customer. One way is to use the inside to tell your customer more about their purchase, thank them or send them a few words of wisdom (Rodríguez-Parada, Mayuet and Gámez 2019).

Offering seasonal and limited-edition packaging in collaboration with artists can turn your packaging into a collector's item, to be reused instead of simply thrown away. Customisation used to be a difficult process due to traditional printing methods, but now with digital printing, the process has become much more flexible. It's a cost-effective solution to be experimented with (Rodríguez-Parada, Mayuet and Gámez 2019).

Using elements of active and smart packaging can represent an upgrade to existing packaging. We can use elements such as RFID tags (these use electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track tags attached to

objects) which contain electronically stored information about the product and provide safety and other information until the end user gets the product. Printed electronics can replace RFID tags. QR codes often contain data for a locator, identifier or tracker that points to a website or application. NFC tags can basically do what QR codes are being used for and more because they use embedded chips. We can also implement augmented reality elements and make a further connection with our client and the brand story that we are selling (Schaefer and Cheung 2018).

Looking beyond the current take-make-waste extractive industrial model, a circular economy aims to redefine growth, focusing on positive society-wide benefits. It entails gradually decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources and designing waste out of the system. Underpinned by a transition to renewable energy sources, the circular model builds economic, natural, and social capital. It is based on these three principles: designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use and regenerating natural systems (Korhonen, Honkasalo and Seppälä, 2018).

It is a critical area and every business needs to pay more attention to avoiding environmental and legal violations that could harm the company's reputation and their customer relationships (Chen and Slotnick, 2015). For alcoholic beverages containing more than 15% alcohol, advertising is prohibited. The advertising message should not encourage excessive alcohol consumption or show positive relationships between drinking alcohol and success in life (Ministrstvo za zdravlje Republike slovenije ,2019)

2 METHODS

2.1 Lean methodology

The main guidelines of lean methodology are to eliminate all uncertainties, work smarter and faster, develop a minimum viable product (MVP) and test it on a regular basis (Maurya A et al. 2016).

After the exact definition we had to detect the problems that we would solve first. The new packaging solution must be a powerful touchpoint and a product that mirrors the brand. Key issues are, do we have a problem that is worth solving, have we created something that people want, how do we accelerate sales growth.

2.2 The Value Proposition Canvas

The Value proposition canvas (Figure 1) is an extract from the Business model canvas and gathers two areas, Customer segment and Value proposition. At the point when we solve all the client's problems and satisfy values, our goal has been achieved (Strategyzer, 2019)

Figure 1: The Value Proposition Canvas

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Client requirements by priorities are functionality, easy assembly, attractive appearance.

With guidelines of lean methodology we identified the priorities for initial risks, we began to systematically test the packaging. After consulting with the client, we decided to use corrugated cardboard. The packaging is not returnable but it is extremely easy to recycle. During the intermediate phases of prototype development, I met and obtained answers from the client that I needed at each stage. We made thirteen prototypes.

The average clients customer is a male aged between 35 and 50, employed, well-placed. The products are in a higher price range and the current packaging solution does not communicate that. The packaging must trigger emotions and offer something more.

Pains on the side of my client are the cost of labour required for packaging, the cost of material, packaging, warehousing, bottles which cannot be packaged in existing packaging because of their size or shape, additional filler used for protection (plastic flakes), adhesive tapes necessary for closing the packaging. For a bottle that cannot be packaged in existing packaging, the client uses a larger one, uses more filler, pays more postage and causes a larger carbon footprint.

My reasons for choosing corrugated cardboard include its low weight, good recyclability and low final cost for the client. It is appropriate for easy application of visual messages and for the final consumer a material that is recyclable (if without additional processing such as laminating, foil blocking, coating etc.).

Gains that my client expects or desires are saving money, time and space, a quality touchpoint that represents the values of the brand and urges customers to continue to consume, sufficient protection for the bottles, one packaging suitable for all segments of bottles. A single solution for all bottles would relieve the packaging process. Clients money is stored in a place where the packaging is stored, in material, money locked in supply, employees and in the value of the packaging itself.

With the flexible packaging solution, client is no longer required to buy an additional filler (plastic flakes) for protecting the bottle. He gained a quality touchpoint that represents the values of the brand and urges customers to continue to consume and has a positive effect on after-sales. The flexible corrugated cardboard packaging offers a possibility of additional advertising, a unique packaging solution that communicates its contribution to the appearance and the brand-creating story.

New packaging enables the buyer to join the brand story, offers him a unique feeling that is recreated with a new story. We can also give the packaging a chance to create a brand, to include customers in various social networks where they connect and socialize, both in the real and the virtual world.

3. 1 Drop test

The penultimate prototype was tested with the client. We did several drop tests (Figure 2). At the fourth drop from 3 metres height with acceleration, the bottom of the packaging was loose but the bottle didn't break. The bottle was smashed at the seventh drop. The testing shows that the most critical parts of the packaging are the bottom and the zipper of the outside layer, the insert works well.

Figure 2: First and seventh drop of a packaging (Andreja Pogačar)

3. 2 Price, weight, assembling speed, touch point comparison

We did a price comparison between three providers (Table 1). Assembly is quite simple and comparable with the old version; with a little practice it goes faster. It is also extremely positive that we don't need any additional plastic flakes for bottle protection. The weight of the new packaging is a few grams lower in comparison with the previous version. And also, we don't need any additional glue for the new packaging.

Table 1: Price, weight, assembling speed, touch point comparison

	Print	Packaging, price without VAT [€/piece]	Large pack. price without VAT [€/piece]	Extra filler [€/packaging]	Weight [g]	Assembling speed	Extra glue	Touch point quality
Pošta Slovenije Old packaging	0/0	1.1393 (official price list)	1.3852 (official price list)	approx. 0.05	1.631 (bottle + filler)	comparable	yes	weak
Eclipse Print d.o.o. Flexible packaging	1/0	1.35 (for 10.000 pcs.)	2.14 (for 10.000 pcs.)	none	1.611 (bottle)	comparable	no	strong
Peakprint d.o.o. Flexible packaging	1/0	1.06 (for 10.000 pcs.)	1.274 (for 10.000 pcs.)	none	1.611 (bottle)	comparable	no	strong

3. 3 Guidelines for graphic design

Outside packaging must merely indicate the content and not reveal it. The outside must provide a sophisticated transition to the inside, so that the opening of the package itself offers us a special sense of reward and treat. The inside offers a surprise and urges the consumer to continue purchasing, enrolling in the community, sharing experiences, building services, using the client's app etc. To get to the content, the entire experience of opening the packaging must be fun and give the consumer a feeling of a gift intended just for him.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Packaging on its own is a waste, but the quality of its design depends on the efficiency of delivery and the protection of the product itself during transport. The client required functional packaging, that can be easily assembled and has an attractive appearance.

The solution is transport packaging with a flexible cardboard insert (Figure 3). It is designed in two dimensions and is appropriate for over 95% of the different bottles distributed by the client. One size fits all shapes up to the volume of a classic litre bottle and the other larger packaging fits the largest dimensions. Packaging is custom made, price-competitive, offers a personalized branding, does not require additional filling of plastic flakes, allows quick assembly, can be easily opened, offers suitable protection and is recyclable.

Figure 3: Flexible packaging (Andreja Pogačar)

Acknowledgements: Project was awarded with Student Prešeren Award ALUO and was created within my master's thesis at the Academy of Fine Arts and Design in Ljubljana under the mentorship of Jure Miklavc and Miha Klinar. The results presented in this case study also include the development that took

5 REFERENCES

Batista, J. (2018). Perception of eco-friendly products through the packaging design – the impact of color and material.

Bernard Vukadin B., Lipovž-Ančič E., Zupančič I. E. (2019). Odpadna embalaža Okoljski kazalci, Agencija RS za okolje, Available at: <http://kazalci.arso.gov.si/sl/content/odpadna-embalaza-4> [Accessed 3rd September 2019].

Carli Lorenzini, G, Olsson, A. (2019) Towards patient-centered packaging design: An industry perspective on processes, functions, and constraints. *Packag TechnolSci.*; 32: 59– 73. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pts.2419>

Chen J, Slotnick S. (2015) Supply chain disclosure and ethical sourcing. *International Journal of Production Economics*,161, pp 17-30.

European Commission (2017) Directive 2009/125/EC [online] Available at: <https://eurlex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:285:0010:0035:en:PDF> [Accessed 3rd September, 2019]

European paper recycling council (2017) Monitoring report, European Declaration on Paper Recycling 2016-2020, Available at: https://www.pita.org.uk/images/European_Declaration_Paper_Recycling_20170410_compressed.pdf [Accessed 3rd September 2019].

Korhonen J, Honkasalo A, Seppälä J. (2018) Circular Economy: The Concept and its Limitations. *Ecological Economics*,143, pp 37-46.

Rodríguez-Parada L, Mayuet P, Gámez A. (2019) Custom Design of Packaging through Advanced Technologies: A Case Study Applied to Apples. *Materials*. 2019;12(3):467.

Maurya A, Mihelić M, Zrimec A, Ries E. (2016) Delaj vitko. Pasadena ,Ljubljana

Ministrstvo za zdravje Republike slovenije (2019) Act on health suitability of foodstuffs and products and materials that come into contact with foodstuffs (Official Gazette of RS, Nos. 52/00 , 42/02 and 47/04 - ZdZPZ)

Schaefer D., Cheung W. M. (2018) Smart Packaging: Opportunities and Challenges, Procedia CIRP, Volume 72,pp. 1022-1027
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2018.03.240>

Singh p.k., Sarkar p. (2019) Eco-design approaches for developing eco-friendly products: a review. In: Shanker k., Shankar r., Sindhvani r. (eds) Advances in industrial and production engineering. Lecture notes in mechanical engineering. Springer, Singapor, pp-185-192

Strategyzer AG S. (2019) Value Proposition Canvas – Download the Official Template [online] Available at: <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/value-proposition-canvas> [Accessed 3rd of September]